

Form generation of piecewise developable surfaces with curved boundaries based on equilibrium equations of membrane shells

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Abstract

Developable surface is generated from a plane by a process of bending deformation that does not involve any in-plane deformation. Developable surface is characterized by vanishing Gaussian curvature throughout the surface. The use of developable surfaces offers a benefit of facilitating the simple fabrication and construction of building materials when designing structures with complex geometries, such as free-form shells. Several studies have proposed generating piecewise developable surfaces that consist of multiple developable surface patches. In this study, we extend our method to generate piecewise developable surfaces with curved boundaries based on the membrane theory of shells. Design parameters are the principal stresses of horizontal projected stresses. Developability of a surface is evaluated using the Gaussian curvature of discrete surfaces in discrete differential geometry. Developable surfaces are obtained by minimizing the sum of squares of the Gaussian curvature at grid points. It is shown that smooth developable surfaces can be generated by appropriately specifying the principal stresses. Additionally, it is shown that the application of line loads along the internal boundaries can create areas of discontinuity in the slope of the shell surface and provide piecewise developable surfaces. Furthermore, we evaluate mechanical properties of generated developable shell surface by finite element analysis.

Keywords: form-finding, shell surface, equilibrium equation, developable surface, discrete differential geometry

1. Introduction

A wide range of methods have been proposed for the design of free form shell structures, such as experimental methods using suspended membrane models [5] and computational methods by numerical analysis and mathematical optimization [10]. Complex shapes such as free form shells present challenges in terms of the complexity in fabrication and construction. To solve these difficulties, application of developable surfaces has been proposed [2]. Developable surface is generated from a plane by a process of bending deformation that does not involve any in-plane deformation. The use of piecewise smooth surfaces consisting of several developable surface patches offers a benefit of facilitating the simple fabrication and construction when designing structures with complex geometries, such as free-form shells.

Developable surface is characterised by vanishing Gaussian curvature throughout the surface. Computation of Gaussian curvature requires complex higher-order derivatives of the function defining the surface shape, especially when parametric representations are used. Since discretization to triangular or quadrilateral elements is needed for structural analysis, it is useful if geometric invariants such as the Gaussian curvature are defined in terms of discrete differential geometry [6]. Various methods using discrete differential geometry have been proposed for designing piecewise developable surfaces. However, optimization method with vertex coordinates as variables often leads to slightly corrugated surfaces when the simple angle defect is used for definition of discrete Gaussian curvature

[9]. Another method using local Gauss maps has been proposed to generate smooth piecewise developable surfaces; however, it is difficult to generate conical or tangent developable surface, and a lot of computation is required if the coordinates of all grid points are regarded as design variables [4]. We presented a method to generate piecewise developable surfaces utilizing the membrane theory of shells and the optimization method [8]. However, its application is limited to surfaces with rectangular boundary. On the other hand, Takeoka *et al.* [11] proposed a method for generating shell surfaces with curved boundaries.

This study combines the methods in Refs. [8] and [11] to generate piecewise developable surfaces with curved boundaries. A parametric form is presented to model the shape of the shell with curved boundary on a plane. Design parameters are the principal stresses of horizontal projected stresses. The shell shape is found by solving the linear system of equilibrium equations. Developability of a surface is evaluated using the Gaussian curvature of discrete surfaces at all internal grid points of the surface based on the angle defect in discrete differential geometry. Developable surfaces are obtained by solving an optimization problem with only a few variables for minimizing the sum of squares of the Gaussian curvature at grid points. It is shown that smooth developable surfaces can be generated by appropriately specifying the principal stresses. Additionally, it is shown that the application of line loads along the internal boundaries can create piecewise developable shell surfaces with discontinuity in the slope along the internal boundary. Furthermore, we evaluate the mechanical properties of generated developable shell surface by finite element (FE) analysis.

2. Form generation of piecewise developable surfaces

In this section, the methods in Refs. [8] and [11] are summarized for completeness of the paper with some extensions to generate more complex developable surfaces.

2.1. Equilibrium equations of membrane shells

Consider a shell structure described as a graph surface on the xy horizontal plane. The vertical z -coordinate of the surface h is defined as a function $h(x,y)$ of x and y . Figure 1 shows a shell element divided by planes parallel to the xz - and yz -planes, respectively, and the stress components on the element. The membrane theory of shells is applied, and accordingly, bending moment and out-of-plane shear forces are not considered. Let s_x and s_y be the in-plane normal stresses along the sections on the planes parallel to the yz - and xz -planes, respectively, which are the stresses in the tangent plane of the shell. t_{xy} and t_{yx} denote the in-plane shear stresses along the sections. The vectors corresponding to s_x , s_y and t_{xy} ($= t_{yx}$) are projected onto the xy -plane to generate the vectors of σ_x , σ_y and τ_{xy} ($= \tau_{yx}$), respectively. Horizontal projected stresses σ_x , σ_y and τ_{xy} are stresses per unit length of the horizontal plane.

Figure 1: Definition of stresses and angles of the shell structure

The horizontal and vertical equilibrium equations are expressed as partial differential equations:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_y}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_x \frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x^2} + 2\tau_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x \partial y} + \sigma_y \frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial y^2} = f \quad (2)$$

where f is the vertical load per unit horizontal projected area of the shell. In this study, the method of Takeoka *et al.* [11] is applied to express the x and y coordinates of the graph surface by the mapping from parameter space $(u, v) \in [0, 1]^2$, respectively, as $x(u, v)$ and $y(u, v)$ to generate surfaces with curved boundaries. The curved boundary is defined using the Bernstein basis functions with respect to the normalized parameters.

The finite difference method discretizes the vertical equilibrium equation. Consider an $N \times N$ uniformly spaced grid in the (u, v) parameter space. The grid point is indicated by (i, j) ($i, j = 1, \dots, N + 1$), and the sizes of grid in u - and v -directions are δu and δv , respectively. The derivatives of h in Eq. (2) are discretized using the central finite difference method, as follows, where $h_{i,j}$ is the h value at the grid point (i, j) :

$$\begin{aligned} & (a^2 \sigma_x + 2ac\tau_{xy} + c^2 \sigma_y) \frac{h_{i+1,j} - 2h_{i,j} + h_{i-1,j}}{(\delta u)^2} \\ & + 2[ab\sigma_x + (ad + bc)\tau_{xy} + cd\sigma_y] \frac{h_{i+1,j+1} - h_{i+1,j-1} - h_{i-1,j+1} + h_{i-1,j-1}}{4\delta u \delta v} \\ & + (b^2 \sigma_x + 2bd\tau_{xy} + d^2 \sigma_y) \frac{h_{i,j+1} - 2h_{i,j} + h_{i,j-1}}{(\delta v)^2} \\ & + \left[\left(a \frac{\partial a}{\partial u} + b \frac{\partial a}{\partial v} \right) \sigma_x + 2 \left(a \frac{\partial c}{\partial u} + b \frac{\partial c}{\partial v} \right) \tau_{xy} + \left(c \frac{\partial c}{\partial u} + d \frac{\partial c}{\partial v} \right) \sigma_y \right] \frac{h_{i+1,j} - h_{i-1,j}}{2\delta u} \\ & + \left[\left(a \frac{\partial b}{\partial u} + b \frac{\partial b}{\partial v} \right) \sigma_x + 2 \left(a \frac{\partial d}{\partial u} + b \frac{\partial d}{\partial v} \right) \tau_{xy} + \left(c \frac{\partial d}{\partial u} + d \frac{\partial d}{\partial v} \right) \sigma_y \right] \frac{h_{i,j+1} - h_{i,j-1}}{2\delta v} = f_{i,j} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where differential coefficients of u and v with respect to x and y are denoted by a , b , c and d for simplicity. In this study, the solution of Eq. (3) is found by solving linear system of equations in the similar manner as Ref. [8], although the successive over-relaxation method is used in Ref. [11]. The left-hand side of Eq. (3) is defined using the variables $h_{i,j}$ and other constant parameters, and the right-hand side is the load value $f_{i,j}$ at the grid point (i, j) . The number of independent variables $h_{i,j}$ excluding those at the fixed points on the boundary is denoted by n .

Let $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denote a vector consisting of the variables $h_{i,j}$, $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ denote a matrix consisting of the coefficients of \mathbf{x} , and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denote a vector consisting of $f_{i,j}$ at free grid points. Equation (3) can be regarded as a linear system of equations with respect to the z -coordinates $h_{i,j}$ of the grid points:

$$\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b} \quad (4)$$

When the solution of Eq. (4) is unique, the variable vector \mathbf{x} is obtained by solving the linear equations.

2.2. Relationship between horizontal projected stress and shell surface shape [8]

The shell shapes derived from the equilibrium equations are influenced by the stress distribution, the

load distribution and the boundary conditions. To facilitate obtaining desired developable surface shape, the horizontal projected stress is assigned so that one of the principal stresses is zero and the vertical load is transferred only in one direction in the proposed method. The load is defined as the sum of distributed and line loads.

In Eq. (2), suppose f on the right-hand side is uniform, and the horizontal projected stresses satisfy $\sigma_x \sigma_y - \tau_{xy}^2 = 0$. This means that the second-order partial differential equation (2) is parabolic [7]. Figure 2 shows the relationship between horizontal projected stresses and principal stresses using Mohr's stress circle. Let σ_1 and σ_2 denote the principal stresses of horizontal projected stresses, and suppose $\sigma_2 = 0$ is satisfied. Then the other principal stress is the sum of the normal direct stress components as $\sigma_1 = \sigma_x + \sigma_y$. If the \hat{x} and \hat{y} axes are taken in the direction of the principal stresses σ_1 and σ_2 as shown in Fig. 2(b), the intersection curve between the equilibrium shape and a plane parallel to $\hat{x}z$ -plane is constant in the direction of \hat{y} -axis where the principal stresses is zero. The vertical equilibrium equation in the $\hat{x}\hat{y}z$ -coordinate system and its solution are expressed as

$$\sigma_1 \frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial \hat{x}^2} = f, \quad h = \frac{f}{2\sigma_1} \hat{x}^2 + C_1 \hat{x} + C_2 \quad (5)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are integration constants. For example, the surface shape becomes a cylindrical shape with the ruling line (generatrix) in \hat{y} -direction and the directrix in \hat{x} -direction, as shown in Fig. 2(b), if the stress σ_1 and vertical load f are uniform and the boundary conditions are defined such that there exists a solution where the surface is straight in \hat{y} -direction. If σ_1 changes linearly in the \hat{y} -direction in Eq. (5), the radius of curvature in the \hat{x} -direction changes linearly and a conical surface can be generated.

To generate piecewise developable surfaces, the loading term on the right-hand side of the equilibrium equation is defined as the sum of distributed loads \bar{f}^S and line loads \bar{f}^L . The gradient of the surface becomes discontinuous when line loads are applied. The line load \bar{f}^L is replaced with a distributed load \bar{F}^L acting on the region of width δw . The right-hand side of Eq. (2) can be expressed as

$$f = \bar{f}^S + \bar{f}^L = \bar{f}^S + \frac{\bar{F}^L}{\delta w} \quad (6)$$

(a) Mohr's stress circle of horizontal projected stress (b) Directions of principal stresses and cylindrical surface

Figure 2: Horizontal projected stress and shell surface shape [8]

2.3. Algorithm for generating developable surfaces using optimization method

The simple developable surfaces presented in Sec. 2.2 can be easily generated by specifying simple distribution of horizontal projected stresses as demonstrated in Ref. [8]. To generate various developable surfaces, this study proposes a method for generating developable surfaces utilizing an

Figure 3: The region Ω_p and the area A_p

Figure 4: Definition of horizontal projected stress by parameter t

Figure 5: Flowchart of the proposed method

optimization method with the parameters defining the distribution of the principal horizontal projected stresses.

Developability of a surface is evaluated using the Gaussian curvature of discrete surfaces. Surfaces discretized into quadrilaterals are divided by diagonals to generate a triangular mesh. Figure 3 shows an internal vertex p and triangles around it. Assuming the discretized Gaussian curvature K_p at vertex p is uniformly distributed in the Voronoi region of the polyhedral surface Ω_p , the discretized Gaussian curvature K_p is expressed using area A_p of domain Ω_p and angle defect as follows [3]:

$$K_p = \frac{1}{A_p} \left(2\pi - \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} \theta_{p,i} \right) \quad (7)$$

The distribution of the horizontal projected stresses is defined by the design variable vector $\mathbf{X} = (X_1, \dots, X_n)$ for the optimization problem. The set of internal vertices of the discrete surface is denoted by \mathcal{P} . The vertices on the internal boundaries that divide each developable surface patch are to be excluded from the set \mathcal{P} . Let $K(\mathbf{X})$ denote the objective function as the sum of squares of the Gaussian curvature at internal vertices in the set \mathcal{P} . The optimization problem is formulated as

$$\text{minimize } K(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}} \{K_p(\mathbf{X})\}^2 \quad (8a)$$

$$\text{subject to } \mathbf{X}^L \leq \mathbf{X} \leq \mathbf{X}^U \quad (8b)$$

where \mathbf{X}^U and \mathbf{X}^L represent the upper and lower bounds for \mathbf{X} , respectively. In this study, the principal stress component σ_1 of the horizontal projected stress is defined using the design variables \mathbf{X} and the parameter $t \in [0,1]$ by the following equation:

$$\sigma_1 = \sum_{i=0}^m X_i B_i^m(t), \quad B_i^m(t) = \frac{m!}{i!(m-i)!} t^i (1-t)^{m-i} \quad (9)$$

where $B_i^m(t)$ denotes the Bernstein basis function of order m . Figure 4 describes the relationship between t and σ_1 defined by the Bernstein basis functions. t is the coordinate in the direction \hat{y} in which the σ_1 value is to be varied. If the units are omitted in the form-finding process, \bar{X}_0 , the value of the principal stress at $t=0$, can be fixed. Additionally, the direction of the principal stress α can be included in \mathbf{X} . In this case, the variables are $\mathbf{X}=(X_1, \dots, X_m, \alpha)$. The flowchart of our proposed method to generate developable surfaces using the optimization is illustrated in Fig. 5.

3. Numerical examples

In this section, the proposed method is applied to generate three shell shapes, and their mechanical performances are investigated utilizing FE analysis. It is demonstrated that the proposed method can provide piecewise developable surfaces. Note that the equilibrium surface shape depends only on the ratio of the projected stresses to the vertical load f per unit projected area. Therefore, for simplicity, the units are omitted in the process of form-finding and f is set to 1. The number of grids in the parameter space is $N = 50$. The form-finding program is created using Python3, and the linear system of the vertical equilibrium equations is solved using the Python library Numpy. The interior point algorithm (trust-constr) [1] of the numerical library Scipy is used to solve the optimization problem. The sensitivity coefficients are computed by using a finite difference approach. OpenSeesPy [12], a Python interpreter of the FE-analysis software OpenSees, is used for linear static analysis. The shell surface is modelled utilizing the quadrilateral isoparametric shell element (ShellMITC4), which considers out-of-plane bending and shear deformations.

3.1. Form generation of piecewise developable surfaces

We consider models where the (x,y) -coordinates are defined by the parameter $(u,v) \in [0,1]^2$:

$$\text{Model 1, 2 : } x = -2(uv^2 - uv - u + 0.5), \quad y = (u+1)(v-0.5) \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Model 3 : } x = -2.5(0.2uv^2 - u + 0.4), \quad y = (uv + v - 1) \quad (11)$$

Note that the plans of the shell models have curved boundary as shown in Fig. 6. The edges shown in red in Fig. 6 indicate that the z -coordinates of the grid points on those edges are fixed in the form generation process. In Model 3, the z -coordinate of fixed boundary on $y=0.5(x+1)$ is defined as $h=0.2(1-x)$. In Models 1 and 2, the principal stress is defined such that $\sigma_1 = \sigma_y$, and other components of horizontal projected stress are assigned as $\sigma_x = \tau_{xy} = 0$, where the principal stress σ_1 is in y -direction. The horizontal projected stress σ_y is defined using the design variables \mathbf{X} and the parameter $t \in [0,1]$ by the following equation:

$$\text{Model 1, 2 : } \sigma_1 = \sigma_y = \sum_{i=0}^m X_i B_i^m(t), \quad t = (x-1.0) / 2.5 \quad (12)$$

In Model 3, the design variables are the direction α and distribution of the principal stress σ_1 as

$$\text{Model 3 : } \sigma_1 = \sum_{i=0}^m X_i B_i^m(t), \quad t = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} \left[x \cos\left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) + y \sin\left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \right] \quad (13)$$

In Model 1 and 3, only the uniform distributed load $f=1$ is applied. In Model 2, in addition to the distributed loads, line loads defined by the following equation are applied to the line shown in green in Fig. 6 to generate a piecewise developable surface.

$$\text{Model 2 : } \bar{F}^L = -(1-t) / 2 \quad (14)$$

Figure 6: Shell domain, definition of fixed nodes and line load in form generation process

Figure 7: Optimum solution: Model 1

Figure 8: Optimum solution: Model 2

Figure 9: Optimum solution: Model 3

Figure 10: Ruling lines of optimum solution shapes

To fix the level of dimensionless stress, the value of the principal stress at $t=0$ is fixed, and X_i ($i=1, \dots, n$) are considered as the design variables. The number of design variables is $n=2$ in Model 1 and $n=3$ in Model 2. In Model 3, the direction of the principal stress α is included in \mathbf{X} and the number of design variables is $n=4$. The initial values, the upper and lower bounds of the variables are assigned as

$$\text{Model 1, 2: } X_i^{\text{init}} = -0.3, X_i^{\text{L}} = -3.0, X_i^{\text{U}} = -0.01$$

$$\text{Model 3: } X_i^{\text{init}} = -0.5, X_i^{\text{L}} = -3.0, X_i^{\text{U}} = -0.01, \quad \alpha^{\text{init}} = \pi/2, \alpha^{\text{L}} = \pi/2, \alpha^{\text{U}} = 5\pi/6$$

Figures 7-9(a) show the optimal shapes of shell surfaces, and Figs. 7-9(b) show distributions of the principal curvature κ . The thickness of the principal curvature line in Figs. 7-9(b) is proportional to the magnitude of the curvature. Figures 7-9(c) show the Gaussian curvature of the surfaces of the optimal solutions. We can confirm that the absolute value of the Gaussian curvature is small for the entire surface except for the internal boundary of Model 2, where a piecewise developable surface with curved internal boundary is obtained. Figure 10 show the directions of ruling lines. Since the ruling lines in Models 1 and 2 intersect with each other at one point, we can see that conical surfaces have been obtained. On the other hand, ruling lines do not intersect with each other at the same point in Model 3. This indicates that the tangent developable surface has been obtained. Table 1 lists the parameters of the initial and optimal solutions of the three models.

Table 1: Optimization results

Model	design variable \mathbf{X}		objective function $K(\mathbf{X})$		Number of iterations
	initial	optimum	initial	optimum	
1	(-0.30, -0.30)	(-0.489, -0.678)	7.63×10^1	1.50×10^{-7}	45
2	(-0.30, -0.30, -0.30)	(-0.648, -0.999, -1.347)	4.87×10^2	6.27×10^{-4}	58
3	(-0.50, -0.50, -0.50, 1.571)	(-0.906, -1.567, -2.096, 2.618)	7.75×10^2	2.24×10^{-2}	71

3.2. Evaluation of mechanical properties by FE analysis

FE analyses are performed for the shell surfaces obtained in Sec. 3.1 to account for elastic deformation. From the coordinates (x, y, h) of a graph surface obtained by the form generation, the respective coordinate values are scaled as $(c_s x, c_s y, c_s h)$ (m) using the scaling coefficient $c_s = 10$ (m) in FE analysis. The shell thickness t_s is 0.1 (m), and vertical distributed load per unit surface area w_s is 2.4 (kN/m²). The vertical load per unit horizontal projected area f is defined as the self-weight of the shell and calculated according to the surface shape. The shells are assumed to be composed of concrete material with Young's modulus $E = 20.0$ (GPa) and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.2$. The displacements along the straight boundaries corresponding to $\nu = 0$ and 1 are fixed in all models. In Model 2, the edge point at $(-10, 0, 0)$ is fixed, on which line load is applied in the form generation process. In Model 3,

the boundary on $x = -10$ is fixed because the principal stress direction is not aligned with the y -axis in the optimum solution. The curved edge of each model is considered to be free boundary.

Figure 11 shows the distribution of vertical displacement of three models. The magenta lines show the fixed boundaries in FE analyses. The maximum vertical displacement and the strain energy of each model are listed in Table 2. We can confirm from these results that the maximum displacements are $1/14492$ and $1/3623$ of the span 20 (m), which are very small, for Models 1 and 2, respectively. The strain energy due to membrane action (in-plane stress) is 65% and 75% for Models 1 and 2, respectively. Figure 12 shows the distribution of principal stress direction in Model 1. The load is mainly transferred by the compressive stress, shown in red, in y -direction, although there are areas where the tensile force exists, shown in blue. In FE analysis, the effects of out-of-plane bending deformation and transverse strain may have led to differences in the stress distributions from those specified in the form generation. Model 3 has a larger maximum displacement that is $1/2350$ of the span 20 (m), and the strain energy due to membrane action is 59%, which is smaller than other models. If the boundary on Model 3 is changed to a free boundary, the maximum displacement is 29 mm, as shown in Fig. 13. This is approximately 3.4 times that of the original.

The results of these FE analyses have confirmed that the piecewise developable surface generated based on the equilibrium equation of the membrane shell against constant vertical load per unit projected area exhibits rational mechanical properties under self-weight, mainly resisting external loads through membrane action. However, it should be noted that appropriate boundary conditions should be specified according to the principal stress directions and loading conditions.

4. Conclusions

A design method has been proposed for generating piecewise developable surfaces by solving an optimization problem to minimize the sum of squares of the Gaussian curvature of the discrete surface. The curved boundary has been defined using the Bernstein basis functions with respect to the normalized parameters. It has been shown that smooth developable surfaces with curved boundaries and sufficiently small Gaussian curvature can be generated by solving an optimization problem with a few design variables utilizing the angle defect for definition of Gaussian curvature. Numerical examples show that it is possible to generate a smooth piecewise developable surface consisting of two developable surface patches. Furthermore, we confirmed by FE analysis that the generated piecewise developable shell has rational mechanical properties under self-weight.

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References

- [1] R. H. Byrd, M. E. Hribar, and J. Nocedal, "An interior point algorithm for large-scale nonlinear programming," *SIAM Journal on Optimization*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 877–900, 1999.
- [2] J. Cui, Y. Zheng, M. Ohsaki, and Y. Luo, "Shape optimization of piecewise developable free-form grid surface using plate components," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 245, pp. 112865, Oct. 2021.
- [3] K. Hayakawa and M. Ohsaki: "Shape design of membrane structure using geometric invariants of discrete surface," *Journal of Structural and Construction Engineering (Transactions of AIJ)*, vol. 86, no. 783, pp. 772–782, 2021. (in Japanese)
- [4] K. Hayakawa, M. Ohsaki, and J. Zhang, "Meshless non-parametric shape design of piecewise approximately developable surfaces using discretized local gauss map," *Journal of the International Association for Shell and Spatial Structures*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 5–14, 2024.

Figure 11: Distribution of vertical displacement (m)

Table 2: Summary of FE analyses

Model	Max. displacement (mm)	Strain energy (Nm) (Ratio (%))		
		Membrane	Bending	Total
1	1.38	85.5 (65.0)	46.1 (35.0)	131.6
2	5.52	115.1 (75.0)	38.2 (25.0)	153.3
3	8.51	240.1 (59.1)	165.8 (40.9)	405.9

Figure 12: Distribution of principal stress (Model 1)

Figure 13: Distribution of vertical displacement (m) (Model 3 with modified boundary conditions)

- [5] H. Isler, “Concrete shells derived from experimental shapes,” *Structural Engineering International*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 142–147, 1994.
- [6] M. Meyer, M. Desbrun, P. Schröder, and A. H. Barr, “Discrete differential-geometry operators for triangulated 2-manifolds,” in *Visualization and Mathematics III*, pp. 35–57, 2003.
- [7] M. Miki and T. Mitchell, “Interactive exploration of tension-compression mixed shells,” *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 41, no. 6, 2022.
- [8] T. Nakajima and M. Ohsaki, “Form generation of piecewise developable surfaces using equilibrium equations of shells,” *J. Struct. Constr. Eng. (Trans. AIJ)*, vol. 89, no. 822, pp. 897–907, 2024. (in Japanese)
- [9] M. Ohsaki and K. Hayakawa, “Non-parametric shape design of free-form shells using fairness measures and discrete differential geometry,” *Journal of the International Association for Shell and Spatial Structures*, vol. 62, no. 2, pp. 93–101, 2021.
- [10] E. Ramm and G. Mehlhorn, “On shape finding methods and ultimate load analyses of reinforced concrete shells,” *Engineering Structures*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 178–198, 1991.
- [11] R. Takeoka, M. Ohsaki, and Y. Sakai, “Non-parametric design of free-form shells with curved boundaries and specified reaction forces,” *Engineering Structures*, vol. 255, pp. 113892, 2022.
- [12] M. Zhu, F. McKenna, and M. H. Scott, “OpenSeesPy: Python library for the OpenSees finite element framework,” *SoftwareX*, vol. 7, pp. 6–11, 2018.